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ECO LINGUISTICS-INFUSED PROCEDURAL TEXT LEARNING FOR ESL STUDENTS' SUCCESS

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Abstract

This research aimed to investigate ESL students' perceptions of the Eco linguistics-based procedural text teaching model and its impact on their learning experiences, particularly concerning the procedural text. A mixed-method approach was employed, involving a purposive sample of 100 undergraduate English department students from the 3rd and 4th semesters at the University of Central Punjab (UCP), Bahawalpur. Data collection utilized 23-item questionnaires, pretests, and posttests. SPSS version 26 analyzed questionnaire and test data, while thematic analysis was applied to open-ended questions. The findings indicated that learners had a positive attitude toward learning English through an eco-linguistics-based procedural teaching approach. Notably, 73% of students expressed satisfaction with the procedural text activities, acknowledging their role in enhancing language skills, particularly in writing. Furthermore, 60% of the participants favored the procedural text teaching model. Crucially, the study revealed significant improvements in writing skills when comparing pretest and posttest results. Learners in the experimental group exhibited higher scores in the post-test, indicating the efficacy of the Eco linguistics-based procedural text model in enhancing procedural text writing skills. In conclusion, this model represents a novel approach to teaching English, emphasizing the importance of environmental values and love. The study suggests that integrating environmental themes into procedural text activities can not only enhance language learning but also promote environmental consciousness among learners. Therefore, it is recommended to encourage the adoption of procedural text writing methods in English language classrooms, with a focus on instilling environmental care and love within the learners, fostering both linguistic and environmental awareness.

Keywords: ESL, Activities, Efficacy, Instilling, Fostering.

Introduction

Procedural texts consist of a series of sequences of instructions designed to achieve a purpose. The main, objective of the procedural text is to describe how to accomplish something through a series of actions or steps (Derewianka, 1990). According to Gerot & Wignell (1994), a procedural text describes how something is completed through a series of processes. Anderson & Anderson (1997), describe procedural text as a text containing instructions for completing a task. He explained the idea that our choice of words will be influenced by our objective and the situation in which we are writing. A procedural text instructs the reader on how to do a specific task (Delpech & Saint Dizier, 2008). This often falls under two categories: how to create something and how to perform an action. According to Derewianka (1990), the objective of a procedural text is to explain how something is carried out through a series of acts or processes. In addition, Eco linguistics is an interdisciplinary topic of study that combines linguistic ecology with language. Ecology is defined as the study of human-environment interactions. Eco linguistics examines not just the relationship between humans, such as the interaction among members of gout speech (speech community) who speak different languages, but also the link between humans and their natural environment. The objective of the English language teaching (ELT) profession is to improve students' ability to produce procedural writings, in the past few years, there have been no significant developments in linguistic description, particularly within the genre of books. One of the most popular proposals for procedural writing was made by Howatt & Widdowson (2004). In 2004, efforts were made to develop a competency-based curriculum, and the Unit Level Curriculum was implemented in 2006. This curriculum combines the attitudes, knowledge, and skills associated with competencies into a single

structure and it is intended to address the social, moral, and religious morals, skills, and knowledge needs of modern society.

Problem Statement

Eco linguistics is an interdisciplinary science that focuses on the study of language and its environment. In Eco linguistics, the interaction between humans and their natural surroundings is examined as well. Environmental values are as important as life. If we love and care about the environment, then we will be able to live happily on this planet. However, in our society, especially in Punjab, students are often taught using traditional methods that encourage rote memorization, turning them into bookworms focused solely on scoring well in exams. Unfortunately, these students are not adequately educated about their love for the environment and environmental values. The question arises: If students are taught through eco-linguistics-based procedural text teaching, do they develop a positive attitude towards the environment? What teaching methods do teachers employ?

Objectives of the Research

1. To understand students' perceptions of the Eco linguistics-based procedural text teaching model with their other learning experiences.
2. To investigate whether the Eco linguistics-based procedural text teaching model positively enhances the development of procedural text writing skills.

Research Questions

1. How do ESL learners perceive the Eco eco-linguistics-based procedural text teaching model in comparison to their other learning experiences?
2. What is the impact of the Eco linguistics-based procedural text teaching model on enhancing the development of writing skills?

Significance of the Study

This research holds significance from various perspectives. It will contribute to a better understanding of learners' perceptions

of Eco linguistic-based procedural text teaching in English. Furthermore, it will assess the effectiveness of the model and address gaps in previous research within the realm of Eco linguistic perspectives. The study is expected to shed light on current research in this field. It is worth noting that this learning process equips individuals with the ability to comprehend the environment, encourages them to behave in an environmentally responsible manner, enables them to accurately analyze the environmental impact on their way of life, and promotes active engagement in public life to support a high-quality environment.

Literature Review

The purpose of a procedural text, as stated by [Derewianka \(1990\)](#), is to explain how something is done by outlining the specific actions that must be taken. [Derewianka \(1990\)](#), adds that the procedure's generic structure includes goals, resources, and actions. The text of the procedure, as defined by [Gerot & Wignell \(1994\)](#), is the text used to explain the actions that make up a process. Moreover, Eco linguistics is a multidisciplinary field that studies the relationship between language and the natural environment. One definition of ecology is "the scientific study of how human activities affect the natural environment." Linguistics is the scientific study of language and its various manifestations, both microscopic and macroscopic ([Kridalaksana, 1985](#), [Kentjono, 1982](#)). Furthermore, according to [McCutchen \(2011\)](#), writing is the most difficult ability to learn. Eco linguistics, then, is concerned with both the human-human relationship and the human-environment relationship; specifically, the relationship between members of a speech (speech community) who speak different languages. [Steffensen & Fill \(2014\)](#), have highlighted the popularity of issues such as linguistic variety, language endangerment, language survival, language death, and language rebirth. Some of these topics have

been discussed in the past. "if diversity is a necessity for successful humanity," one of the Eco linguistic studies states, "then linguistic diversity must be maintained, as language is at the center of what it is to be human." On the other hand, arguments that praised biological diversity were an effective antecedent for proponents of language diversity. More recently, a study conducted by [Syahrotun \(2016\)](#), using a qualitative-descriptive method found that instruction manuals can be utilized to instill environmental concerns. Consistent with the findings of other studies, he suggests that educators make innovative use of texts grounded in eco-linguistics. He took note of the various approaches the educators took to teaching English as a foreign language. His research was based on 26 observations from 8 different instructors, as well as 48 interviews with students and professors. Based on his research into the educator community, he concluded that educators create their unique pedagogical philosophies in an ever-evolving fashion. To a large measure, teachers' styles are shaped by the communities in which they work and live. Similar findings were reached by [Shirvan \(2017\)](#), who used the ecological model to investigate the causes of anxiety in college students, concluding that these factors operate on a hierarchical scale. Researchers have examined several aspects of language education and instruction from an ecological viewpoint. First used by [Steffensen & Kramersch \(2017\)](#), this approach delves into the intertwined factors that shape IT. As [Maharani \(2017\)](#), suggested that writing is one of the skills that students must exert additional effort to learn. Recently, [Fariha & Setiawati \(2021\)](#), conducted research on anxiety among Saudi students of English as a foreign language.

Research Methodology

A quantitative research design was adopted, and the methodology of the research was quantitative.

Population and Sampling

According to the definition provided by [Best & Kahn \(2009\)](#), A group of people that have a common characteristic and are of interest to the researcher in their entirety is referred to as a population. Keeping in mind the objectives of the research the researcher selected English as a second language (ESL) learners studying in the Department of English, University of Central Punjab (UCP) as the population of the research. To conduct this research the researcher used the purposive non-random sampling technique in his research. For data collection, the University College of Punjab was selected and 100 students (sections A, B) of BS English 3rd and 4th semesters were selected as a sample for data collection. For test purposes, 60 students were selected from both sections in equal proportion.

Research Instruments

According to [Parpala & Lindblom-Ylänne \(2012\)](#), a research tool is an instrument for gathering, measuring, and analyzing data about your topic. To obtain accurate results from the data collected from respondents the researcher used observation, questionnaire, and test as research tools. An adapted version of the "classroom observation system" developed by the University of San Diego (available at <http://newscenter.sdsu.edu>) was used for observation. The questionnaire was employed to know the English as second language (ESL) learners' perceptions of the Eco linguistics-based procedural text teaching model about other learning experiences, and it was revised from the model of [Bloom's Taxonomy \(1956\)](#) modifications and amendments by [\(Anderson & Krathwohl 2001\)](#). The researcher used a questionnaire with some modification that was used by [\(Widayanti, Rustyana et al. 2019\)](#). Five-point Likert scale was used in the questionnaire.

The researcher took a pre-test from the respondents and their grades were marked. Then, the respondents were given lectures about procedural text teaching models and they were taught almost for a month. The researcher then took a post-test to determine the learning gained through the specific thirteen-day treatment.

Data Collection and Data Analysis

Data collection refers to the process of acquiring, measuring, and analyzing accurate information to conduct research using standardized and validated techniques. A questionnaire with 23 statements was filled out by respondents to know about their impressions of Eco linguistics task-based procedural text teaching. Students were given a task on environmental value, and they understood the concept of procedural writing in English while being instructed by the teacher. Their activities were monitored and the outcomes were recorded. The learners were motivated and educated about environmental love and care, and then they were given another task about all of the procedures that were taught and practiced in English after a few days. Their activities were noted and they were given grades. In the end, a comparison was made and the results were analyzed. Open-ended questions were asked about the ways and steps they use in class to teach the procedural text. The data gathered by the questionnaire was evaluated using statistical tools like Social Sciences Statistics Package (SPSS). In scoring the students' composition writings, the researcher used [Hughes's theory \(1992:91-93\)](#)

Findings and Discussion

The study was conducted to determine English as a second language (ESL) learners' perceptions of the Eco linguistics-based procedural text teaching model, and its effects on the writing skills and vocabulary of the learners. The analysis of respondents' questionnaires and tests reveals these notes mentioned as under:

Gender	Frequency (f)
Male	50
Female	50
Total	100

The table and graph show the Frequency (f) of the participants gender-wise. There were both male and female learners equal in proportion.

Table 2: The learners' perceptions of Eco linguistics-based procedural text teaching model (see Appendix A)

Figure 1: The Response of Students' Perceptions of Procedural Text Teaching Model

Table and Figure 2 show the response of students' perceptions about the procedural text teaching model. The results of the data exhibit that the mean score of 13 items (items no. 1,2,3,4,5,6,8,9,10,11,12,13, 14, 15) fall in the criterion of acceptance and 7 items fall in the criterion of rejection indicate that the effects of social media on English language learning. It was seen that 73% of students were satisfied with the statement that the procedural text activities improved their language skills. A majority of 67% of students

were satisfied, while 33% were dissatisfied, that the Eco linguistics-based procedural teaching approach aids in the acquisition of new vocabulary. The responses of respondents showed that 64% of students agreed and 29 % of students were unsatisfied with the statement that the way of teaching in teaching writing in the procedural text is fun. The majority of 56 % of students were satisfied and 38 % of students were unsatisfied that they liked learning English through an Eco linguistics-based procedural teaching approach. 58% of students were satisfied and 42% of students were unsatisfied that they liked learning English language skills (listening, speaking, writing, reading). The majority 58% of students were satisfied and 42 % of students were unsatisfied that they liked procedural text writing. The majority of 57 % of students were satisfied and 43 % of students were unsatisfied that they think that writing is one of skills that is difficult to learn. The majority of i.e.,55 % of students were satisfied and 45 % of students were unsatisfied that they understood the writing lessons through the Eco linguistics-based procedural teaching approach that has been applied by my teacher. The majority 62% of students were satisfied and 38 % of students were unsatisfied with the guidance of a teacher, I feel motivated to ask questions about things that they have not already understood about procedural text writing. The majority of 54% of students were satisfied and 46 % of students were unsatisfied that they know about Eco linguistics-based procedural text. The majority of 64% of students were satisfied and 36 % of students were unsatisfied that they think the way of teacher teaches writing in procedural text is fun. ". The majority of 53 % of students were satisfied and 47 % of students were unsatisfied that the Eco linguistics-based procedural teaching approach boasts care and love for the environment. The majority of 62 % of students were satisfied and 38% of

students were unsatisfied that they feel comfortable when studying or writing using the procedural text teaching approach. The majority of 56 % of students were satisfied and 44 % of students were unsatisfied that they faced problems in obtaining information when studying the Eco linguistics-based procedural approach. The majority of 64% of students were satisfied and 36 % of students were unsatisfied that I prefer learning through a procedural approach rather than other approaches.

Table 3: Effect of Eco linguistics-based Procedural Text Teaching Model on Language Skills (see Appendix B)

Table 3 shows the response of students about the effect of the procedural text teaching model on language skills. The results of the data exhibit that the mean score of 8 items (item no. 16,17, 18.....24) fall in the criterion of acceptance and 4 items (item no. 5,6,7 and 8) fall in the criterion of rejection which indicate that the effect of procedural text teaching model on language skills. The majority 55% of students were satisfied and 45% of students were unsatisfied that they think the procedural text teaching model positively enhances the ratio of learning writing skills. The majority 65% of students were satisfied and 35 % of students were unsatisfied by learning through the procedural text teaching model, I can write a great introduction to the topic with examples. The majority of 57% of students were satisfied and 43% of students were unsatisfied that the Procedural text activities made me able to comprehend the

concepts of the text. The majority of 73% of students were satisfied and 27% of students were unsatisfied that the Procedural text activities improved my language skills. The majority of 68% of students were satisfied and 32 % of students were unsatisfied that the Procedural text activities improved my contextual vocabulary. The majority of 62 % of students were satisfied and 38 % of students were unsatisfied that the Procedural text activities improved my writing skills. The majority 55 % of students were satisfied and 45 % of students were unsatisfied that they understood the writing lessons through the Eco linguistics-based procedural teaching approach that has been applied by my teacher. The majority of 62% of students were satisfied and 38 % of students were unsatisfied that their Learning through Eco linguistics-based procedural approach increased my achievements.

Table 4: Comparison of pre-test and post-test of the control groups of both Male and Female Students

Gender	pair	N	Mean score	Std. Deviation	t-value	Sig.
Male	Pre-test	15	4.39	1.380	-2.132	0.043
	Post-test	15	4.62	1.134		
Female	Pre-test	15	4.65	1.038	-2.312	0.034
	Post-test	15	5.39	1.431		

The above table reveals the difference in results in the pretest and posttest about both the control group male and female students. The scores of male students of the control group in the pre-test indicated outcomes as (M = 4.39, SD = 1.380), while the results in the post-test were (M = 4.62, SD = 1.134). The results of the posttest of the control group were better than the results of the pretest. The comparison of the pre-test and post-test means reveals a statistically very minute difference between the two sets of findings. The scores of female students of the control group in the pre-test indicated outcomes as (M = 4.65, SD = 1.038), while the results in the post-test were (M = 5.39, SD = 1.431). The results of the posttest of the control group were better than the results of the pretest.

The comparison of the pre-test and post-test means reveals a statistically minute difference between the two sets of findings. It was obvious from the findings of both pretest and post-test that female learners of the control group scored better as compared to the male learners of the control group.

Table 5: Comparison of pre-test and post-test experimental groups of both Male and Female Students

Gender	pair	N	Mean score	Std. Deviation	t-value	Sig.
Male	Pre-test	15	4.44	0.780	-3.587	0.011
	Post-test	15	6.04	1.939		
Female	Pre-test	15	4.87	0.451	-4.752	0.009
	Post-test	15	7.27	1.682		

The results in the above table reveal that the significance level of the pre-test and post-test about male students of the experimental group (0.011) is less than 0.05 i.e., level of the significance. The scores of the experimental group of male students in the pre-test indicated outcomes as (M = 4.44, SD = 1.939), while the results in the post-test were (M = 6.04, SD=0.780). The results of the posttest experimental group were better than the results of the pretest. The comparison of the pre-test and post-test means reveals a statistically significant difference between the two sets of findings. The scores of the experimental group of female students in the pre-test indicated outcomes as (M = 4.87, SD 0.451), while the results in the post-test were (M = 6.27, SD 1.682). The results of the posttest experimental group were better than the results of the pretest. The comparison of the pre-test and post-test means reveals a statistically significant difference between the two sets of findings. There is a great mean difference in the post-test results of both male and female learners of the experimental group. Both male and female students scored more in the post-test while female learners scored more in the post-test than the male students. From the p values of both groups of male and female English as a second language (ESL) learners p values are less than the level

of significance which means the test implication of the treatment to the experimental group of both male and female students was valid. The scores of students of the control group in pre-test indicated outcomes as (M = 4.39, SD = 1.380), while the results in the post-test were (M = 4.62, SD = 1.134). The results of the posttest of the control group were better than the results of the pretest. The comparison of the pre-test and post-test means reveals a statistically minute difference between the two sets of findings. It was obvious from the findings of both pretest and post-test that female learners of the control group scored better as compared to the male learners of the control group. The scores of the experimental group of male students in the pre-test indicated outcomes as (M = 4.44, SD = 1.939), while the results in the post-test were (M = 6.04, SD=0.780). The scores of the experimental group of female students in the pre-test indicated outcomes as (M = 4.87, SD 0.451), while the results in the post-test were (M = 6.27, SD 1.682). The results of the posttest experimental group were better than the results of the pretest. From the p values of both groups of male and female English as a second language (ESL) learners p values are less than the level of significance which means the test implication of the treatment to the experimental group of both male and female students was valid. The purpose of this research was to bring improvement to the traditional classroom environment. During the research, English as a second language (ESL) learners were provided a conducive environment to develop their oral skills using positive politeness strategies. Participants thought that they understood the writing lessons through the eco-linguistics-based procedural teaching approach applied by their teacher. The research focused on English as a second language (ESL) learners studying at the college level. The research began with gathering the descriptive data through

questionnaires, which were formulated to know learners' perceptions about the procedural text teaching model. The researcher distributed questionnaires among the learners to determine the learners' perceptions. The results of the questionnaire show that 54% of the learners knew about the model and liked learning through the procedural text teaching model. In addition to that, it was discovered that students were satisfied that with the guidance of a teacher, they felt motivated to ask questions about things that they had not already understood about procedural text writing. Respondents were given two essays to write as a pre-test by the researcher. One group was the control group, while another was used as a test subject. The findings were noted. Participants in the study were instructed on essay writing over ten days utilizing the procedural text teaching paradigm. After ten days, participants in both groups were instructed to compose the same essays. The outcomes were different this time around. The experimental group had a higher score than the control group on the test. Overall, the study achieved its primary goal. During the application of the model in the experimental group, it was observed that students' participation drastically increased, and they were more enthusiastic and interested in the performing tasks of the class. Each student showed significant improvement in responding to questions and holding discussions. Students frequently shared their problems and met the teacher personally to find a solution for them. Students verbally state that they feel very light during classroom activities and forget even if they are tired.

Conclusion

It was clear from observation that the instructors were teaching English as a second language using different teaching methods like GTM, DM, CLT, TRP, SP, etc. These results are in line with previous research (Rani, 2020, Mohammad Rizqi & Akbar, 2016). The second

research objective, whether an Eco linguistics-based procedural text teaching model positively enhances the ratio of learning by writing the procedural text or not, was also supported by the study. For this purpose, the following three basic stages of learners' pre-learning outcomes as a result of prevailing methodologies in the institution, implementation of the model, and the post-learning outcomes as a result of treatment were adopted and tests were taken from English as a second language (ESL) learners. Pretest and post-test results proved significant differences in grades concerning writing skills. The results showed that learners scored more on the post-test than on the pretest. This shows that teaching writing through the procedural text had a greater influence on learning a second language and vocabulary as well. The findings of the learner's response, the effect of the given model on writing skills, revealed that they think the procedural text teaching model positively enhances the ratio of learning writing skills.

Recommendations

The findings of the study may apply to a wider population, even though it was only carried out on a small scale. Some implications can be drawn from the findings of the study. The instructors should take into account the unique characteristics of each of the pupils in the classroom, the atmosphere in the classroom should be welcoming, and it should be carefully examined whether or not to employ a variety of instructional approaches. It would be interesting to investigate language students at a variety of universities to determine the environmental elements that contribute to the acquisition of a second language in the context of future research. The comparison of language classes at public and private-sector universities, as well as the comparison of universities from other regions, can bring to the forefront a more comprehensive picture of the difficulties surrounding the environment. As

part of the implementation of the curriculum, the educational authorities are expected to provide support for the learning and development of the procedural texts that are based on Eco linguistics.

References

- Anderson, L. W. and D. R. Krathwohl (2001). A taxonomy for learning, teaching, and assessing: A revision of Bloom's taxonomy of educational objectives, Longman.
- Anderson, M. and K. Anderson (1997). Text types in English, Macmillan Education AU.
- Best, J. W. and J. Kahn (2009). Research in Education New Delhi, Printice Hall of India Pvt, Ltd.
- Delpech, E. and P. Saint Dizier (2008). Investigating the structure of procedural texts for answering how-to questions. Language Resources and Evaluation Conference (LREC 2008).
- Derewianka, B. (1990). Exploring how texts work, Heinemann.
- Fariha, M. R. and P. Setiawati (2021). "STUDENTS' PERCEPTION TOWARD THE USE OF EDMODO
- Gerot, L. and P. Wignell (1994). Making sense of functional grammar: An introductory workbook, Antipodean Educational Enterprises Queensland.
- Howatt, A. P. R. and H. G. Widdowson (2004). A history of ELT, Oxford university press.
- Kentjono, D. (1990). Dasar-dasar linguistik umum, Fakultas Sastra Universitas Indonesia. Khatulistiwa 3(1).
- Kridalaksana, H. (1986). Kelas kata dalam bahasa Indonesia, Gramedia Pustaka Utama.
- Maharani, M. M. (2017). IMPROVING STUDENTS' WRITING THROUGH DIARY WRITING. Proceedings Education and Language International Conference.
- McCutchen, D. (2011). "From novice to expert: Implications of language skills and writing-relevant knowledge for memory during the development of writing skill." Journal of writing research 3(1): 51-68
- Parpala, A. and S. Lindblom-Ylänne (2012). "Using a research instrument for developing quality at the university." Quality in Higher Education 18(3): 313-328
- Rani, R. (2020). "An Ecological Study of English Language Learning Anxiety: A Case Study of National Textile University." NUML Journal of Critical Inquiry 18(1): 64-VIII.
- Rizqi, M. (2016). ACTIVE VOICE CHANGES IN TRANSLATION FROM ENGLISH TO INDONESIAN AND VICE VERSA. Metalingua: Jurnal Penelitian Bahasa, 14(2), 197-208.
- Shirvan, M. E. (2017). Iranian English language learners' attitude towards their accent in English language: An ecological approach. Englishes in Practice, 4(1), 1-30.
- Steffensen, S. V. and A. Fill (2014). "Eco linguistics: the state of the art and future horizons." Language sciences 41: 6-25.
- Steffensen, S. V. and C. Kramsch (2017). "The ecology of second language acquisition and socialization." Springer International Publishing. doi 10: 978-973.
- Svensson, L. (1984). Three Approaches to Descriptive Research.
- Syahrotun, S. (2016). Analisis Kemampuan Pemecahan Masalah Matematis Siswa Sekolah Menengah Pertama di Kota Bandung (Doctoral dissertation, Universitas Pendidikan Indonesia).
- Widayanti, T., et al. (2019). "Students' Perception in Writing Procedure Text." Professional Journal of English Education 2(5): 687-691. writing." Psychological reports 99(1): 51-73.
- Widayanti, T., Rustyana, N., & Haryudin, A. (2019). Students' Perception in Writing Procedure Text. Professional Journal of English Education, 2(5), 687-691.

Appendix A

Statement		SA	A	N	DA	SDA	Mean (\bar{x})	SD
1. I like learning English through an Eco linguistics-based procedural teaching approach.	<i>f</i>	35	21	6	10	28	2.63	1.443
	%	35%	21%	6%	10%	28%		
2. I like learning English language skills (listening, speaking, writing, and reading).	<i>f</i>	33	40	8	10	9	2.64	1.412
	%	33%	40%	8%	10%	9%		
3. I like procedural text writing.	<i>f</i>	27	31	9	22	11	2.57	1.415
	%	27%	31%	9%	22%	11%		
4. I think that writing is one of the skills that is difficult to learn.	<i>f</i>	24	33	3	12	28	2.64	1.293
	%	24%	33%	3%	12%	28%		
5. I understand the writing lessons through the Eco linguistics-based procedural teaching approach that has been applied by my teacher.	<i>f</i>	29	26	9	17	19	2.59	1.518
	%	29%	26%	9%	17%	19%		
6. With the guidance of a teacher, I feel motivated to ask questions about things that I have not already understood about procedural text writing.	<i>f</i>	24	38	8	19	11	2.57	1.390
	%	24%	38%	8%	19%	11%		
7. I feel difficulty when reading procedural texts.	<i>f</i>	23	36	7	16	18	2.33	1.387
	%	23%	36%	7%	16%	18%		
I know about the eco-linguistics-based procedural text.	<i>f</i>	16	38	7	13	26	2.52	1.348
	%	16%	38%	7%	13%	26%		
8. I feel difficulty when writing Eco linguistics-based procedural texts.	<i>f</i>	24	39	9	9	19	2.52	1.332
	%	24%	39%	9%	9%	19%		
9. I think the way of teaching teaches writing in the procedural text is fun.	<i>f</i>	29	35	7	11	18	2.55	1.393
	%	29%	35%	7%	11%	18%		
10. Eco linguistics-based procedural teaching approach boasts care and love for the environment.	<i>f</i>	23	30	8	19	20	2.56	1.329
	%	23%	30%	8%	19%	20%		
11. I feel comfortable when studying or writing using a procedural text teaching approach.	<i>f</i>	28	34	8	9	21	2.57	1.440
	%	28%	34%	8%	9%	21%		
12. I believe that learning with Eco's linguistics-based procedural approach is effective.	<i>f</i>	22	44	5	12	17	2.52	1.425
	%	22%	44%	5%	12%	17%		
13 I face problems in obtaining information when studying the	<i>f</i>	26	30	6	14	24	2.48	1.279
	%	26%	30%	6%	14%	24%		

Eco linguistics-based procedural approach.								
14 I prefer learning through a procedural approach rather than other approaches.	<i>f</i>	28	36	7	11	18	2.46	1.397
	%	28%	36%	7%	11%	18%		
Cumulative Mean (\bar{x})		25.06%	34.07%	7.138%	13.866%	19.866%	2.51	1.371

Appendix B

Statement		SA	A	N	DA	SDA	Mean (\bar{x})	SD
1. I think the procedural text teaching model positively enhances the ratio of learning writing skills.	<i>f</i>	31	24	6	13	26	2.58	1.533
	%	31.0%	24.0%	6.0%	13.0%	26.0%		
2. By learning through the procedural text teaching model, I can write a great introduction to the topic with examples.	<i>f</i>	37	28	5	16	14	2.64	1.354
	%	37.0%	28.0%	5.0%	16.0%	14.0%		
3. <i>Procedural text</i> activities make me able to comprehend the concepts of the text.	<i>f</i>	29	28	6	14	23	2.57	1.384
	%	29.0%	28.0%	6.0%	14.0%	23.0%		
4. <i>Procedural text</i> activities improve my language skills.	<i>f</i>	40	33	4	17	6	2.54	1.350
	%	40.0%	33.0%	4.0%	17.0%	6.0%		
5. <i>Procedural text</i> activities improve my contextual vocabulary.	<i>f</i>	33	35	9	14	9	2.32	1.259
	%	33.0%	35.0%	9.0%	14.0%	9.0%		
6. <i>Procedural text</i> activities improve my writing skills.	<i>f</i>	33	29	12	6	20	2.28	1.240
	%	33.0%	29.0%	12.0%	6.0%	20.0%		
7. Eco linguistics-based procedural teaching approach helps learn new vocabulary.	<i>f</i>	29	26	9	17	19	2.35	1.224
	%	29.0%	26.0%	9.0%	17.0%	19.0%		
8. Learning through an eco-linguistics-based procedural approach increased my achievements.	<i>f</i>	22	40	7.0	13	18	2.27	1.395
	%	22.0%	40.0%	7.0%	13.0%	18.0%		
Cumulative Mean		31.75%	30.375	7.25	13.75	16.87	2.47	1.364

APPENDIX- C:

Questionnaire for Students

This questionnaire is designed on “The Effects of Eco linguistics- Based Procedural Text Teaching Model on Teaching English Writing to English as second language (ESL) Learners”. Your response will remain confidential. The data will be used for research purposes. Your cooperation will be highly valued.

Section A: personal information (Optional)

Name _____

Gender _____

Class _____

Institution _____

Section B: Instruction

Please respond to the following questions by ticking off the suitable. Each of the question has five points where 1=strongly disagree ,2= disagree,3 =not sure ,4 =agree, and 5= strongly agree. Thank you for responding to this questionnaire.

Appendix – D:

Classroom Ecological Observation Sheet

Day: _____ Setting: _____

Teacher: _____ Start Time: _____ End Time: _____

CHARACTERISTICS Demographic Composition of Students: Total Number: _____

Gender	Punjabi	Urdu	Saraiki	Sindhi	Pushto
Male					
Female					

Sketch Classroom Arrangement:

(Identify position of student, teacher, peer comparisons, etc.

Lesson/Content:

Language(s) of Instruction:

Teaching Method:

Instructional Materials:

Materials used by Student:

Is this a "typical" school day? class session? ___ yes; ___ no.

If no, explain:

CLASSROOM OBSERVATION SYSTEM: ECOLOGICAL REFLECTIONS

Student _____ Date _____ Observer: _____

Describe physical characteristics of the classroom:

Describe classroom atmosphere/climate:

Describe the teacher's instructional style:

Describe the teacher's management style:

Describe peer interactions in the classroom:

CLASSROOM OBSERVATION SYSTEM: PSYCHOEDUCATIONAL REFLECTIONS

Student _____ Date _____ Observer: _____

Describe student's overall engagement in classroom processes. Compare to classmates.

Compare across tasks/processes.

Describe the teacher's interactions with this student. Compare to classmates.

Describe this student's interactions with peers. Compare to classmates.

APPENDIX – E: Activity for The procedural texts

Participant's Name: _____

Gender _____

Age _____

Class _____

Write a Procedural text based on the topics below.

Choose one of the topics below:

How to make coffee?

How to make fried rice?

APPENDIX – F: Test for learners

Recycling of plastic bottles plays an important role in reducing land pollution. Briefly explain the recycling process of plastic bottles.